

REVIEW OF POLYMERS AND COMPOSITES JOINING WITH MICROWAVE ENERGY

Shuangjie Zhou and Martin C. Hawley
*Department of Chemical Engineering and Materials Science
Michigan State University
East Lansing, MI 48824*

ABSTRACT: Microwave processing is an emerging technology that offers a number of advantages over thermal heating in a wide range of applications. Microwaves provide high-speed and energy efficient heating because of the unique mechanism of molecular level coupling. Microwave heating is also selective because microwaves can be more easily absorbed by materials with higher dielectric loss properties. These advantages have been recently utilized in joining polymers and composites. This paper offers an overview of the research and development regarding the application of microwave joining. Fixed frequency and variable frequency joining processes in microwave multi-mode and single mode applicators are reviewed and compared. In multi-mode applicators such as domestic microwave ovens, various heating patterns are excited at the same time. In single mode resonant applicators, only one heating pattern is excited at one time and microwave energy is more efficiently coupled into the materials. These studies demonstrated that reduced cycle time was obtained with adequate joint strength in microwave joining compared with thermal process. Uniform processing methods, such as variable frequency sweeping in multi-mode applicators and mode switching in single mode applicators, are reviewed. Existing and potential future industrial applications of microwave joining are also discussed. Challenges in this new process are identified and possible future directions are outlined.

KEYWORDS: microwave, joining, polymers, composites, ceramics

INTRODUCTION

Polymer composites and ceramics are widely used as structural parts in aerospace, military, and automotive industries. Some applications require these parts to have complex shapes, which is difficult to obtain from direct molding. Joining has been a useful approach to make complex shaped parts and also assemblies composed of dissimilar materials. Joining is also widely used in repairing structural composites.

Microwave processing is an emerging technology that offers a number of advantages over thermal heating in a wide range of applications. Microwave refers to electromagnetic waves in the frequency range from 300MHz to 300GHz or the characteristic wavelength range from 1m to 1mm. Microwaves provide instantaneous and energy efficient heating because of the unique mechanism of molecular level coupling. Microwave heating is inside out with heat loss at the boundaries whereas thermal heating depends on temperature gradient and the surface is heated first. Sometimes hybrid microwave-thermal heating is utilized to achieve more uniform processing. Microwave heating can be easily controlled by very fast changes in the applied electric field whereas thermal heating is characterized with long lag times and difficulty for composite cure control. In microwave heating, the heat source can be readily removed to prevent thermal excursion. Microwaves have been used to process a wide variety of materials including polymers and composites. In polymer processing, both thermosets and thermoplastics have been studied. The drying process of various thermoplastics with microwave energy has been investigated [1].

Microwaves have also been used to cure thermosetting materials, including polyurethanes [2], polyimides [3,4] and epoxies [5-11]. Both pulsed and continuous microwave curing of epoxies have been studied [5,10]. In composites processing, both batch [12,13,14] and continuous processes [10,15] have been developed. Demonstrated results in microwave processing of polymers and composites include increased polymerization rate [3,7-9], reduced drying time for pelletized polycarbonate and polypropylene [1], increased T_g for cured epoxy [6], enhanced fiber/matrix adhesion in carbon composites [12], and increased mechanical strength of graphite/epoxy composite [10].

When applied in joining, microwave energy offers an important advantage of selective heating. In microwave joining, a microwave absorber is usually placed at the interface. Microwave energy is directly transferred into the absorber and heats it rapidly, even though the materials to be joined are very thick. An illustration of microwave joining is shown in Figure 1. The energy can be focused on the joint with precision without large impact on the bulk material properties. Microwaves have been used in joining ceramics, welding thermoplastics, and joining polymeric materials with adhesives. These studies are reviewed separately in the following sections.

Figure 1. Illustration of Microwave Joining

MICROWAVE JOINING OF CERAMICS

Microwaves have been used in joining oxide ceramics and ceramics composites. Aravindan and Krishnamurthy [16] joined alumina – 30% zirconia with microwave hybrid heating using sodium silicate glass as the interlayer absorber. It was observed that the temperature rose to 1000°C within 2 minutes because of the microwave absorption by the interlayer. No external pressure was applied. A wavy texture was obtained over the interface. This wavy texture can enhance the joint quality by facilitating mechanical interlocking of the interlayer material with the bulk composites. In addition, possible elemental diffusion across the interface may also contribute to the joint strength. Lee and case [17] used microwaves to join polycrystalline alumina (sintered with microwaves) and a commercial mica platelet reinforced glass ceramic (MaCor™). Both materials were polished and coated with silica film and then joined in a microwave single mode cavity. No external load was applied. The sintered polycrystalline alumina was joined at temperatures between 1605°C and 1665°C. The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) study indicated that the best joints obtained were essentially indistinguishable from the parent materials. The MaCor™ specimens did not join when heated with microwaves at 1000°C and 1025°C for

20min, partly joined at 1075°C for 20min and 1hr, and joined at 1150°C but the MaCor™ specimens warped at this high temperature because the maximum recommended use temperature of the MaCor™ was 1000°C. Lee and case [17] also studied microwave repair of ceramics. A commercial polycrystalline alumina specimen was indented at 48N and 98N. The indented specimens were heated with microwaves at 1500°C for 1hr. Both the 98N cracks and the 48N indents healed completely in microwave heating, as opposed to only partial healing in thermal heating of 48N indents under the same conditions (1500°C for 1hr). This indicated microwave enhanced the mass diffusivity, either via the “microwave effects” or by intense local heating. Fukishima et al. [18] joined several purities of alumina ranging from 92% to 99% alumina with microwaves. The joining temperatures were from 1400°C to 1850°C and the external loads were from zero to 2.4MPa. The 92% and 96% alumina were joined directly without the use of an interlayer and the joint strength approached the original strength of the materials. This direct joint formed via an existing glassy grain-boundary phase, which can become viscous at very high temperatures. The 99% alumina could not be directly joined and an interlayer of 92% or 96% was used to form a successful bond. The bending strength of 90% of the original material was obtained. Cozzi et al. [19] used microwave hybrid heating to join 99.5% alumina in a modified domestic microwave oven and compared the results with thermal joining. An interlayer of 94% alumina was used. The joining temperatures were from 1450°C to 1550°C and the pressures were from 1 to 3MPa. The flexural strength of the specimens was significantly affected by the temperature, but not significantly affected by the pressure or heating method.

Microwaves have also been applied in joining non-oxide ceramics. Lee and Case [20] used conventional and microwave heating to join silicon carbide (using Blackglas™ as interlayer) and magnesium fluoride (using sodium silicate as interlayer). Thermal heating was done in a nitrogen environment in a conventional furnace. Microwave joining was done in air in a 2.45GHz single mode resonant cavity. The SiC samples were first heated in the conventional furnace at 900°C for 20min, then some samples were microwave heated at 1200°C for 20min and others were thermally heated at 1200°C for 20min. Though SiC is a microwave susceptor, the microwave joined parts had similar bond layer (thickness and appearance) as that joined with conventional heating method. The MgF₂ samples were heated at 700°C for 20min in both microwave and thermal processes. The MgF₂ joint obtained from both processes had a similar thickness about 10µm.

MICROWAVE WELDING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

In microwave welding of thermoplastics, the microwave absorber placed at the joint line is selectively heated up and then heat is conducted into the bulk to form molten layers and cause fusion bonding. Wu and Benatar [21] studied microwave welding of high density polyethylene (HDPE) bars using conductive polyaniline (PANI). A mixture of the PANI powder and the parent material powder was used as the absorber gasket. The PANI concentrations in the mixture were 50% and 60%. The welding was done in a domestic microwave oven (multi-mode oven). After the welding, the PANI usually remains at the interface, and the joint strength is limited by the strength of the PANI. But under special conditions the PANI can be squeezed out and the joint strength approaches the parent material. Experiments showed that applying pressure during the heating phase was not beneficial for the joint formation. The HDPE in the gasket was melted first, and the gasket was squeezed out before a thick enough molten layer could form in the bulk. So in the subsequent experiments, no pressure was used in the heating phase. The pressure applied in the cooling phase was varied from 0.3MPa to 0.9MPa. It was observed that increasing the welding pressure (in the cooling phase) led to an increase in the joint strength, because most of the weaker gasket could be squeezed out. Using the 60% PANI gasket, a tensile joint strength equal to that of the HDPE was obtained with a heating time of 60s and a welding pressure of 0.9MPa.

When higher concentrations of PANI are used in the absorber gasket, a thicker molten layer needs to be formed in order to squeeze out the gasket so that the joint strength can approach that of the parent materials. Hence the welding cycle is longer. Wu et al. [22] microwave welded HDPE bars with the PANI concentrations lowered to 5% and 10% in the absorber composites. Two conducting PANI materials (HCl doped and Versicon) were used. An impedance matching system was used to improve the energy transfer efficiency. The use of the impedance matching microwave system reduced the welding time to 40 seconds, and reduced the PANI concentration in the absorber layer to 5% with a joint strength of 90% of the bulk material strength. It was expected that the joint strength could be further enhanced by increasing the welding pressure, heating time and power.

Staicovici et al. [23] also studied the welding and disassembly of HDPE bars with both untuned and tuned microwave systems. If sufficient absorber gasket remains at the joint line after welding, it can be reheated with microwaves to disassemble the parts for recycling. With the untuned microwave system, the maximum tensile joint strength of 60% of the parent material could be disassembled with a high power of 2000W for 120 seconds. With the tuned system, the maximum tensile joint strength that could be disassembled increased to 80% of the bulk material. At the same time, the power was reduced to 1000W and the disassembling time was reduced to 30 seconds.

Wise and Froment [24] used a microwave multimode cavity to weld two thermoplastics, i.e. unreinforced polypropylene and transparent acrylic. A variety of microwave susceptible implant materials were used. Results showed that microwave joints with good qualities could be obtained using implants from three main identified loss mechanisms - conduction, dielectric and ferromagnetic. Among these implant materials, carbon was identified as probably the most economic implant component for microwave welding. Metallic film was not an efficient implant because perfect conductors reflect microwaves totally. Possible implant introduction methods were also studied for solid and liquid implants. During welding, the pressure was 7.5MPa in most cases. The microwave power ranged from 440W to 2200W and the time was from 10 seconds to 120 seconds. In mechanical testing, failures occurred in the bulk rather than in the joint in many cases including with implants made from PANI and carbon black.

MICROWAVE ADHESIVE BONDING OF POLYMERIC MATERIALS

Microwaves have also been used in adhesive bonding of polymeric materials in multi-mode or single mode applicators. In multi-mode applicators, several modes are excited at the same time. In single mode resonant applicators, only one mode is excited at one time and the field pattern is more defined than that in multi-mode applicators. The interface can be placed at the strongest field to maximize the energy efficiency. Uniform heating methods have been applied in the bonding [25-28] and the methods are different for multi-mode and single mode cavities.

Paulauskas et al. [29] studied fixed frequency microwave adhesive bonding in a multi-mode applicator. Glass and glass fiber reinforced urethane-based composite (SRIM-part) were adhesive bonded with Goodrich 582E (epoxy based) adhesive. The relationship between input power level and bonding time was studied. Additives such as carbon black were added into the adhesives to improve the lossy characteristics of the adhesive. It was reported that during microwave bonding, the coupling of microwave energy into the adhesives was highly efficient. The coupling was further enhanced with the additives. Compared with thermal adhesive bonding, fixed frequency microwave bonding techniques reduced the required curing time significantly while obtained an equal or slightly higher ultimate tensile strength of the bonded assemblies. Paulauskas et al. [25] also applied variable frequency microwave (VFM) in adhesive bonding in a multi-mode cavity. The frequency is rapidly swept over a selected range

to launch different electric field patterns into the applicator sequentially. If the frequency range is well selected and wide enough, then the overall heating can be uniform. An advantage of VFM bonding over fixed frequency technique was that VFM had a more uniform time-averaged electric field. Thus VFM did not readily create localized overheating in the adhesive or the substrates and was not sensitive to sample position. Compared with fixed frequency microwave bonding, VFM reduced the bonding time slightly.

Wei et al. [26] performed VFM bonding of polymer composites for automotive application and bonding of flip-chips (FC) for electronic packaging application. A multi-mode applicator was used. In the automotive application, SRIM (chopped glass fiber reinforced, urethane-based composite) and Rynite® 5309 (glass fiber/mineral reinforced thermoplastic polyester composite) panels were studied. Reduced bonding cycle was achieved with adequate bonding strength. Uniform bonding was observed. In electronic packaging application, VFM curing of the underfill and bonding of the chips were performed. The VFM curing cycle was much shorter than the thermal curing cycle. In Flip-Chip (FC) bonding experiments, high IC integrity of the bonded chip was obtained with VFM process. In addition, VFM cured samples had 50% reduction in stress compared with thermal cured assemblies.

Zhou et al. [27,28] used an epoxy-based adhesive to bond two polymeric materials, a glass reinforced ethylene/methacrylic acid copolymer (Bexloy W502, DuPont) and a nylon 6 and ethylene/methacrylic acid copolymer (Surlyn SG201U, DuPont). A cylindrical single mode cavity was used. The sample setup (for single lap shear test) and temperature measuring points are shown in Figure 2. The adhesive was applied between two substrate panels 1 and 2. A supporting panel was used to prevent deformation of the bond. Several glass beads (0.6mm diameter) were embedded in the adhesive to control the thickness of the bond. The objective was to heat up the adhesive selectively and cure it to form the bond. The adhesive temperature was measured at five points across the adhesive. The substrate temperature was measured at one point to confirm the substrates were not substantially heated up. The dimensions of the adhesives in the cavity are shown in Figure 3.

T1~T5: Adhesive Temperature; T6: Substrate Temperature

(b)

Fig. 2. Sample setup for adhesive bonding: (a) side view, and (b) top view

Figure 3. Dimensions of the Adhesive in the Cavity

Preliminary experiments showed that heating with one microwave mode resulted in temperature gradient as high as 60°C across the adhesive, as shown in Figure 4. Therefore a variable frequency method was applied to improve the heating uniformity. In a single mode cavity, frequency-sweeping is not an efficient approach to create time-averaged uniform field distributions, because microwaves are not efficiently coupled into materials at non-resonant frequencies and most power gets reflected. Instead, several modes with complementary heating patterns can be excited distinctively and alternatively in the single mode cavity to obtain time-averaged uniform heating. This method is referred to as “mode switching”. By switching among the selected resonant modes, the energy efficiency and heating uniformity can be highly improved. In this study, two modes were used during the processing, mode TM020 (2.8450GHz, heats the center of the adhesive) and mode TM212 (3.3830GHz, heats the edge of the adhesive). The theoretical electric field patterns of the two modes are shown in Figure 5. Lighter regions represent higher electric field strength. Since polymers are non-magnetic materials, the electric field patterns can represent the heating patterns. Figure 5 shows that the selected two modes have complementary heating patterns. In the microwave adhesive bonding process, the heating was switched between the two modes and the temperature gradient was reduced to 10°C across the adhesive, as shown in Figure 6. The substrate temperature was much lower than the adhesive temperatures.

(a) Heating Pattern of Mode TM020

(b) Heating Pattern of Mode TM212

Figure 4. Heating Pattern with One Microwave Mode

(a) Theoretical E field Pattern of Mode TM020 in Empty Cavity
 (b) Theoretical E field Pattern of Mode TM212 in Empty Cavity
 Figure 5. Theoretical Electric Field Patterns in Empty Cavity

Figure 6. Temperature Profiles of Mode-switching Microwave Bonding of the Bexloy Assembly (Uniform and Selective Heating of the Adhesive)

For the Bexloy substrates, the highest bonding temperature was set at 120°C. The microwave bonding time was totally 20 minutes (8 minutes heating up and 12 minutes isothermal bonding at 120°C). Thermally bonded assemblies were also prepared under normal pressure for comparison. The bonding time was approximately 100 minutes at 120°C. Six coupons were tested with single-lap shear equipment. The crosshead displacement rate was 0.127 cm/minute. Results are shown in Table 1 for the Bexloy assembly. The shear strength of microwave bonded samples was significantly higher than that of thermally bonded ones, though the ultimate extent of cure was about the same (99%, analyzed with Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)) for both microwave and thermal processes. In the single lap-shear testing, microwave bonded assemblies all broke in the substrate, indicating that the interface and the adhesive were stronger than the substrate. On the other hand, thermally bonded samples all broke at the interface. The adhesion in thermal samples might be improved with proper surface treatment of the substrates. For Surlyn substrates, the microwave bonding temperature was set at 100°C, because the substrate surface adjacent to the adhesive would degrade if the bonding temperature was higher than 100°C. The microwave bonding cycle was totally 51 minutes (6 minutes heating up and 45 minutes isothermal bonding at 100°C). Some assemblies were also bonded in a thermal oven. However, thermal bonding at 100°C was too slow. Therefore the thermal bonding temperature was set at 120°C. The approximate time for the thermal bonding at 120°C was 100 minutes. The results of bonding strength of the Surlyn assembly are shown in Table 2. Microwave bonded assemblies at 100°C for 51 minutes

obtained the same strength as thermally bonded assemblies at 120°C for 100 minutes. Both microwave and thermally bonded assemblies broke in the substrates in single lap shear test. Among the materials used in literature and in this study, only Bexloy W502/Eccobond A401-37 assemblies obtained much higher strength in microwave bonding compared to thermal process. This could result from a variety of factors and was not further investigated in this study.

Table 1. Bond conditions and strength of Eccobond/Bexloy assembly with microwave or thermal method

Bonding Conditions	Break Pattern	Shear Strength (MPa)
Microwave 8 min heat-up, 12 min isothermal bonding at 120°C	Shear in Panel	5.80 ± 0.79
Thermal 100 min at 120°C	Shear at interface	3.23± 0.46

Table 2. Bond conditions and strength of Eccobond/Surlyn assembly with microwave or thermal method

Bonding Conditions	Break Pattern	Shear Strength (MPa)
Microwave 6 min heat-up, 45 min isothermal bonding at 100°C	Shear in Panel	6.14±1.02
Thermal at 120°C for 100 minutes	Shear in Panel	6.06±0.48

APPLICATIONS

Industrial uses of microwaves in joining are relatively new technologies. Examples of industrial applications are in the packaging and assembly processes in electronic industry, such as Flip Chip underfill cure in smart card assemblies, structural bonding of electronic assemblies, optoelectronic and fiber optic devices, and so on [30]. In Flip Chip packaging, an underfill adhesive is applied between the chip and the substrates to reduce the mismatch of coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between the silicon chips and the substrates. Low temperature substrates are desirable because of their low cost. However the optimum cure temperatures of the underfill exceed the tolerable temperature of the substrate. In thermal processing, the solution is to either use higher cost substrates or cure the underfill at lower temperatures with prolonged time. The selective heating feature of the microwaves allows curing the underfill rapidly without overheating the substrates. The significant reduction in cycle time leads to reduced cost. Microwave joining has application potentials in many other markets too, such as in automotive assembly. The most prominent advantage of using microwaves is increased processing speed, which leads to increased product throughput. The process also offers potentials for improved product quality and reduced cost.

CONCLUSIONS

Results of the microwave joining efforts are specific to the materials studied. But some compelling advantages were observed in most studies. Microwaves are concentrated at the joint area without substantially heating up the bulk materials to be joined. Hence the properties and dimensions of the bulk

are not significantly affected. Also the energy efficiency is high and the joining time is reduced. Microwave technology holds promise in industrial joining and repair of ceramics, plastics and composites. However, much work still needs to be done, such as:

- Design and manufacture specialized tooling applicable to microwave processing.
- Design low-cost and versatile microwave systems with standardized plug-in microwave components and automation capabilities.
- Understand industry needs and organize pilot-scale research to study process scale-up, large-scale process control and automation, material characterization, and equipment prototyping.
- Create user-friendly software for design of microwave systems and applicators suitable for specific processing needs.
- Compile a database including existing material dielectric properties, proper dielectric measurement techniques, process-related physical and chemical properties, and microwave processing cases, e.g. the rubber industry success.
- Further fundamental research including determination of microwave effects, accurate temperature measurement, and reliable and repeatable dielectric analysis tools.
- Provide complete and realistic economic analysis for various microwave processes.

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